

D3.4

Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site- Specific risk parameters and stressor indicators

Project name

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes

Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069941

Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Dissemination level	Public (PU) - fully open
Type of deliverable	R - Document, report
Work package	WP3 – Atmospheric Forcing Modelling, Weather Now/Fore-Casting and Data Processing
Deliverable number	D3.4 Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-specific risk parameters and stressor indicators
Status - version, date	Final – V1.0, 11/02/2025
Deliverable leader	AUTh
Contractual date of delivery	31/12/2024
Keywords	Operational Weather Prediction, Atmospheric Stressors, Data Assimilation, Mesoscale Modelling, Model Validation, Environmental Data, Climate Downscaling, impact indicators

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Didier Bousmar	SPW MI	05/02/2025
Peer review 2	Alina Beatrice Raileanu	UDG	06/02/2025

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of changes
0.1	06/11/2024	AUTh	First draft of document
0.15	03/02/2025	AUTh	Second draft ready for review
0.19	10/02/2025	AUTh	Final draft after review
1.0	11/02/2025	AUTh	Final submitted version

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
3D	Three Dimensional
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
AUTh	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
BMA	Block Maximum approach
COP	Common Operational Picture
DTR	Diurnal Temperature Range

Abbreviation	Meaning
ECA&D	European Climate Assessment & Dataset
ETCCDI	Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices
EURO-CORDEX	The European branch of the international CORDEX
EVT	Extreme Value Theory
EZM	European Zooming Model
FD	Frost Days
GCM	Global Climate Model
GEV	Generalized Extreme Value
GP	Generalized Pareto
grib2	Gridded Binary two format
ICON	ICOsahedral Nonhydrostatic (the global NWP model of Deutcher Wetterdienst)
ICON-EU	Nested regional ICON model for Europe region
ID	Icing Days
IMS	Incident Management System
IWW	Inland WaterWays
LU	land use
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
OMS	Operational Modelling System
POT	Peaks-Over-Threshold
R95pTOT	Total precipitation over very wet days
R99pTOT	Total precipitation over extremely wet days
RCM	Regional Climate Model
RT	Real time
Rx5day	Maximum five-day precipitation
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
TKE	Turbulent Kinetic Energy

Executive Summary

This deliverable, titled “*D3.4 - Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-specific risk parameters and stressor indicators*”, aims to outline a new methodology developed by AUTH for the continuous update and refinement of numerical modelling results based on in-situ measurements. This approach relies on a 3D data assimilation protocol, enabling the integration of data streams from meteorological and hydrological stations in the selected use case areas. Specifically, the data collected from the sensor networks, delivered through the monitoring system, is initially compared with simulated data and subsequently analysed and integrated (including aggregation, synchronization, calibration, and assimilation) via a fully interoperable data management platform. This method explicitly introduces local-scale atmospheric and climate stresses on the Inland WaterWays (IWW) infrastructures and the connected land infrastructures of selected use cases, which are otherwise unresolved, into high-resolution simulations.

Furthermore, this deliverable aims also to provide a detailed description of the qualitative and quantitative assessment of the primary and secondary impact indicators derived from climate calculations and real-time (RT) in-situ measurements. These indicators will subsequently be used in WP5-WP7 of PLOT0 as inputs for generating the climatic risk assessment corresponding to the selected transport infrastructures and the expected damages associated. The data used in the analysis described in this document originates from the EURO-CORDEX project, leveraging multiple Regional Climate Model (RCM) simulations performed by various Global Climate Models (GCMs) to cover the period from 1971 to 2100. The climatic variables considered in this analysis include ambient temperature and precipitation.

A key component of this deliverable is the validation of the newly implemented data assimilation framework within the Operational Modelling System (OMS). By integrating real-time weather station data into the model, this methodology enhances forecast accuracy, particularly at the microscale level. The system undergoes continuous performance evaluation, with statistical indicators computed daily to assess the reliability of nowcasting and forecasting outputs. A year-long pilot study in 2024 demonstrated that the assimilation of real-time observations led to significant improvements in the precision of meteorological simulations, ultimately enhancing resilience planning for IWW infrastructures.

Additionally, the deliverable examines the long-term implications of climate change on IWW infrastructure resilience by analysing ETCCDI indices under different emission scenarios (RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5). The results, visualized for the moderate RCP4.5 scenario, offer valuable insights into evolving climate stressors such as temperature extremes and changing precipitation patterns. These findings support strategic adaptation planning and the development of robust mitigation measures to ensure the long-term sustainability of inland waterway transport systems.

1. Introduction

1.1 Project information

The project entitled **“Deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes (PLOT0)”** aims at increasing the resilience of the IWW and the connected hinterland infrastructures, especially under adverse conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents, and other kinds of hazards. In doing this, downscaled climate change scenarios will be combined with simulation tools and actual data, to provide operators an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels.

PLOT0 project consists in the deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies, and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes. An integrated tool is set up to allow relevant authorities to improve the efficiency of their infrastructures management. This tool is a combination of downscaled climate change scenarios with simulation tools and actual data. Six complementary avenues will be considered to achieve this integrated tool that will support relevant authorities and their operators for more effective management:

- Measure and use high-resolution modelling data for the determination and assessment of the climatic risk of the selected transport infrastructures and associated expected damages.
- Use existing data from various sources with new types of sensor-generated data (computer vision) to feed the used simulator.
- Utilise tailored weather forecasts (combining seamlessly all available data sources) for specific hot spots, providing real-time early warnings with corresponding impact assessment.
- Develop improved multi-temporal, multi-sensor UAV- and satellite-based observations with robust spectral analysis, computer vision and machine learning-based assessment for diverse transport infrastructures.
- Design and implement an integrated resilience assessment platform environment as an innovative planning tool that will permit a quantitative resilience assessment through an end-to-end simulation environment, running “what-if” impact/risk/resilience assessment scenarios. The effects of adaptation measures can be investigated by changing the hazard, exposure, and vulnerability input parameters.
- Design and implement a Common Operational Picture (COP), including an enhanced visualisation interface and an Incident Management System (IMS).

The PLOT0 integrated platform and its tools will be validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania and Hungary.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

This document is an output of Task 3.5 “Dynamical Data Assimilation of meteorological and climate data from sensors” and Task 3.6 “Assessment of primary and secondary site-specific climate risk parameters and atmospheric stressor indicators” of the PLOT0 project, contributing to the continuous improvement and updating of numerical modelling results based on in-situ measurements and reporting on indicators of extreme climate for a future reference period. More specifically, the present

deliverable focuses on the methodologies, approaches, and techniques employed to produce refined meteorological and climate data for the most critical parameters relevant to the resilience of the IWW infrastructures. Furthermore, it emphasizes the development and provision of some suitable indicators for assessing climate impacts on the broader areas of interest surrounding these infrastructures within the PLOTTO use case areas.

1.3 Intended audience

The primary audience of this deliverable report consists of the PLOTTO partners involved in the tasks exploiting the final downscaled data and results obtained using the methods reported here, see Sec. 1.4. The secondary audience is the whole PLOTTO consortium. Finally, this deliverable is intended for public use, and it is open to any interested audience.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relationship with other work packages/deliverables

The Deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 1. Describes PLOTTO's aim, as well as this document's purpose, intended audience and structure.
- Section 2. Describes the context and general methodology of this Deliverable.
- Section 3. Describes the modelling approaches and techniques for the downscaling.
- Section 4. Presents the results of the model validation and assessment of extreme indices.
- Section 5. Concludes the Deliverable by summarising the main outcomes.

The outcomes of Tasks 3.5 and 3.6 as described in this deliverable will be used to provide input in WP6 and WP7, as described in Section 2.

2. Methodology

The core concept behind the PLOTO methodology is the creation of a robust data assimilation layer that ensures real-time observational data are seamlessly integrated into the simulation framework. This process allows real-world measurements to be accurately transformed into simulation parameters, which then feed back into the model, continuously refining its outputs. By using actual in-situ data, the system can dynamically adjust its predictions, resulting in more accurate and reliable forecasts. This approach is particularly valuable in the context of managing the Inland Waterway (IWW) infrastructures, where real-time data can significantly improve the resilience against extreme weather events and environmental stressors.

To implement this, AUTH has developed and validated a 3D data assimilation system that leverages information collected from meteorological stations deployed in the PLOTO pilot areas. This system has been carefully calibrated to optimize its performance, ensuring that the data assimilation process integrates seamlessly with the existing Operational Modelling System (OMS). By continuously feeding real-time measurements into the model, it can adjust predictions on an hourly basis, allowing authorities to respond more effectively to emerging hazards.

The integration of this 3D data assimilation system within the PLOTO project provides a powerful tool for enhancing the accuracy of high-resolution meteorological forecasts. By utilizing sensor data, the system not only corrects the existing model predictions, but also improves the spatial and temporal resolution of the forecasts. This enables PLOTO to deliver actionable insights for infrastructure managers, ensuring that IWW networks can better withstand the adverse conditions. The continuous calibration and validation of this system mean that it can adapt to the changes of the environmental conditions, providing a more resilient and adaptive approach to infrastructure management.

To achieve a consistent understanding of changes in weather and climate extremes within the PLOTO project, the methodology draws upon the standardized indices defined by the ETCCDI (Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices). These indices are designed to characterize various aspects of the extreme events, such as their frequency, intensity, and persistence (Klein Tank et al., 2009). Specifically, the core set includes 27 indices related to ambient temperature and precipitation, which are widely used to assess and monitor trends in climate extremes (Peterson and Manton, 2008; Alexander et al., 2006). These metrics are essential in evaluating how well global and regional climate models can simulate the moderate extremes, providing insights into projected future changes.

In the context of PLOTO, using these standardized indices allows for a robust analysis of climate extremes impacting Inland Waterways (IWW) infrastructures. By assessing changes in these indices, the project can derive valuable insights into the future climate risks, helping infrastructure managers to develop effective adaptation strategies. Additionally, employing a uniform approach to characterize and analyse extremes ensures consistency in the results, enabling comparisons across different pilot areas and regions covered by PLOTO. This standardization is crucial for understanding the broader impacts of climate change on IWW networks.

Beyond the core set of ETCCDI indices, the PLOTO project may incorporate additional indices tailored to specific adaptation needs of the pilot regions. For instance, the ECA&D project has defined extra indices focusing on temperature extremes, while stakeholders in Southeast Asia have proposed indices to track the onset and end of the monsoon season (Klein Tank et al., 2009). Similarly, PLOTO can adapt

these flexible indices to address unique climatic challenges faced by its pilot areas in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary, ensuring that the assessments are both region-specific and aligned with global standards.

Operational output from the OMS is consolidated and uploaded through the PLOTTO middleware to support the operation of IWAT and other PLOTTO components, implemented and demonstrated in WP6 and WP7. Furthermore, accumulated series of forecast variables will become available for further analysis in the impact assessment modules of WP4.

3. Modelling Methods and Procedures

3.1 Mesoscale Model Calculations

3.1.1 Overview

An operational modelling module (OMS) has been developed by AUTH within the scope of WP3 Task 3.4 to predict and identify extreme climate indicators and atmospheric stressors related to specific hazards. This module offers capabilities for downscaling temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed, and cloud cover fields through real-time forecasting of key meteorological parameters. The work performed in Task 3.5 involved the assimilation of data aggregated from the sensor network into the OMS, continuously updating and refining the numerical results.

3.1.2 Mesoscale Computational Tool

The section of the OMS dedicated to calculating meteorological parameters operates similarly to most systems running on a continuous basis. Specifically, OMS features two distinct operational modes—nowcasting and forecasting—which are managed through a scheduler infrastructure that controls a series of grid-based meteorological model simulations. For this purpose, the mesoscale meteorological model MEMO (Moussiopoulos et al., 2012), part of the EZM (European Zooming Model) system (Moussiopoulos, 1995), is employed. MEMO is a three-dimensional, non-hydrostatic, prognostic model designed to simulate mesoscale airflows and the dispersion of inert pollutants across complex terrains, supporting multiple nesting levels for local-to-regional scale applications.

The MEMO model effectively generates simulated hourly meteorological datasets, including parameters like wind speed and direction, temperature, turbulent kinetic energy (TKE), solar radiation, cloud cover (diagnostically), and relative humidity. Additionally, it calculates turbulence characteristics such as surface roughness, Monin-Obukhov length, and friction velocity at multiple heights within a 3D grid covering the target area. These high-resolution downscaled datasets provide flexible options for data extraction. A key feature of MEMO is its ability to model local atmospheric systems, including mountain-valley winds, sea/lake breezes, and urban heat islands, which influence dispersion phenomena on local and regional scales. Thus, MEMO serves as an effective tool for generating detailed meteorological data for downscaling and atmospheric pollutant dispersion applications.

For MEMO initialization, vertical profiles of key meteorological variables from the ICON-EU (Zängl et al., 2015) numerical weather prediction model are incorporated every three hours. ICON-EU operates on an icosahedral grid, offering high-resolution forecasts (horizontal spacing of 6.5 km in native grid and 7 km in output grid) and 60 vertical levels up to 22.5 km. Forecast data are provided in intervals of one hour up to 78 hours and in three-hour intervals for forecasts extending from 81 to 120 hours.

The automated module's downloader retrieves ICON-EU data through the PLOTTO middleware, decompresses and converts the data from grib2 format to ASCII, and stores them in a dynamic data pool within the middleware. The scheduler then selects the latest dataset to input into MEMO. Each process logs events and diagnostic files, accessible to other PLOTTO components through the middleware repository.

3.1.3 Configuration of Mesoscale Computational Tool

The OMS has been configured for the three pilot areas in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary as part of the PLOTO project. The MEMO grid setup for each area is detailed in Table 1, while Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate the domain extents and the topographical layers that provide a high-resolution representation of the terrain across the modelled areas.

Table 1: Specification and dimensions of OMS domains.

Use Case A (Romania)				
Coarse Grid			Units	UTM zone
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	635546	5002753	m	35 T
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	240	240	cells	
X,Y size of each cell	1000	1000	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	240000	240000	m	
Fine Grid				
Use Case B (Budapest)				
Coarse Grid			Units	UTM zone
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	352109	5257038	m	34 T
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	72	72	cells	
X,Y size of each cell	2000	2000	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	144000	144000	m	
Fine Grid				
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	352109	5257038	m	34 T
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	144	144	cells	
X,Y size of each cell	250	250	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	36000	36000	m	
Use Case C (Wallonia)				
Coarse Grid			Units	UTM zone
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	662274	5568490	m	31 U
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	120	120	Cells	
X,Y size of each cell	2000	2000	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	240000	240000	m	
Fine Grid				
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	685702	5616158	m	31 U
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	120	120	Cells	
X,Y size of each cell	250	250	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	30000	30000	m	

For the necessary high-resolution topographical input data, NASA’s Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM/90 m) database was utilized. Additionally, thematic layers of land use data were obtained from the Corine Land Cover 2006 database, which includes 44 land use (LU) types. These were reclassified

into the seven LU types used in MEMO applications: water, arid land, sparse vegetation, farmland, forests, suburban, and urban.

Figure 1: Domain boundaries and topography regarding the Use Case of Romania.

Figure 2: Domain boundaries and topography regarding the Use Case of Budapest.

Figure 3: Domain boundaries and topography regarding the Use Case of Wallonia.

3.1.4 Mesoscale Model Calculations

The meteorological mesoscale module within the PLOTTO framework offers functionalities for downscaling various meteorological parameter fields, including temperature, humidity, solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, cloud cover, and wind intensity and direction. In nowcasting mode, model outputs are available on an hourly basis for the current hour and provide short-term forecasts for the next three hours. In forecasting mode, results are produced hourly across the 24-hour period of the following day (00:00 – 23:00). These outputs are automatically processed using Python-based post-processing tools, generating a variety of maps, time series, and statistical indices relevant to predefined climate and atmospheric risk factors.

In nowcasting mode, the system provides high-resolution, downscaled meteorological fields for the areas of interest each hour, which are automatically processed to produce maps, time series, and indices for various climate and atmospheric risk indicators. In forecasting mode, 24-hour simulations are driven by ICON-EU prognostic data to produce daily sets of downscaled parameter graphs for all designated areas. Both operational datasets are subsequently stored in the PLOTTO middleware (c.f. PLOTTO Deliverable D3.3). Table 2 presents the output specifications for both modes.

Table 2: Specification of the output of nowcasting and forecasting modes.

Parameter (unit)	Time reference	Spatial Resolution	Vertical Reference
Temperature (°C)	1 h	250 m for Wallonia and Budapest 1000 m for Romania	2 m
Relative Humidity (%)			10 m
Wind Speed (m/s)			Surface
Wind direction (°)			-
Precipitation (mm)			
Cloud Cover (%)			

3.2 Data Assimilation Approach

Scientists commonly rely on ground-based monitoring to gather information on meteorological and climate conditions, as it generally provides the most accurate estimates. This approach works well when assessing very limited areas or when the monitoring data is representative of a broader region. However, local measurements often lack spatial representativeness, which can be problematic in urban areas where complex flow patterns, influenced by urban structures, lead to significant variations in local meteorology (Denby et al., 2009). Enhancing the spatial representativeness of monitoring data can be achieved by incorporating supplementary data sources, which offer broader spatial coverage. Such supplementary data may include distances from significant topographical features, land use information, and satellite data. Although spatial statistical methods can utilize these data directly, meteorological models are better suited for describing the relevant physical processes, providing high spatial and temporal resolution data that can improve the monitoring data's coverage (Denby et al., 2009). A primary limitation of modelling, however, is its higher level of uncertainty compared to monitoring data. Therefore, an optimal approach would be to combine monitoring and modelling data sources to produce comprehensive spatio-temporal meteorological maps.

3.2.1 Methodological Background

Several terms are used to describe the combination of different data sources. Interpolation refers to methods that primarily use monitoring data, and possibly additional supplementary data, to estimate meteorological parameters at any location in space (e.g., Beelen, 2009). Spatial interpolation techniques are broadly divided into two categories: deterministic approaches and geostatistical methods. Deterministic methods rely on predefined mathematical equations to predict values at unsampled locations, weighing the values of known sample points without capturing the spatial structure of the data (URL). In contrast, geostatistical methods aim to fit a spatial model to the data, enabling prediction at unsampled locations and providing accuracy estimates. Common deterministic techniques include TIN, IDW, and Trend surface analysis, while geostatistical methods include kriging and its variants (Isaaks and Srivastava, 1989). For the current application, the kriging method has been employed.

In addition, combining multiple data sources involves data fusion and integration approaches, which combine datasets through geometric or statistical optimization methods. Data fusion and interpolation

generally do not adhere to physical or chemical constraints but are mainly limited to statistical constraints (Denby et al., 2009). Data assimilation, on the other hand, is a modelling technique that directly incorporates monitoring data into model simulations during the modelling process. Here, measured data guide the model towards an optimal solution consistent with the model's physical framework. The most common data assimilation techniques are variational methods (Elbern et al., 1999), often used in meteorological forecasting, while other methods, such as Ensemble Kalman filters (van Loon et al., 2000), are also applicable.

In this approach, a combination of data fusion and data assimilation methods is used within the OMS to incorporate observational data. The modelling tools complement sensor data on meteorological parameters with high-resolution spatial and temporal predictions, highlighting potential hazardous or stressful conditions. Observational data are integrated hourly and assimilated into model calculations using a spatial interpolation method (kriging – Goovaerts, 1997). An automated module downloads and quality-checks the sensor data before feeding them into the interpolation module. A spatial and temporal analysis algorithm distinguishes outliers caused by accumulated errors from genuine local extremes, which are either corrected or excluded.

Kriging, a widely used geostatistical method for spatial interpolation, involves multiple steps, including exploratory statistical analysis, variogram modelling (Webster and Oliver, 1993), surface creation, and exploration of a variance surface. In spatial statistics, a variogram describes the degree of spatial dependence within a random spatial field. The theoretical variogram models often used include spherical, exponential, power, and logarithmic functions, making kriging especially suitable when there is spatially correlated distance or directional bias in the data.

To further ensure that observational network data are accurately integrated, continuous online quality checks and statistical evaluations are performed against measurements from traditional monitoring devices. Model results and measurements undergo additional offline processing to validate simulations and detect diurnal, seasonal, or spatial patterns that may warrant further correction factors.

3.2.2 Data Assimilation Module

Computational core

The integration of measurement data is accomplished through a system that combines data fusion (assimilation) and computational data analysis (reanalysis) by using both measurement data and archived hourly forecasts from the OMS for the targeted areas.

A newly developed feature has been added to the system, enabling it to reconstruct meteorological fields across the entire area of interest for any period with available data from both measurements and MEMO model calculations. To quantify and estimate the total uncertainties in the derived meteorological fields, uncertainties and representativeness errors from primary measurements, as well as the various types of uncertainties associated with the model results, are considered.

This process can be performed manually, allowing the operator to select specific start and end dates, or it can be applied automatically during operational nowcasts and forecasts. For the automated operation, this computational feature has been incorporated into the OMS core, enabling real-time corrections to the simulated meteorological fields. In this regard, the reanalysis function has been added to the system's operational schedule and the list of functions available for manual use.

The computational process is managed by a scheduler that coordinates the collection of all available data—both from measurements and model results—for a predefined period across the four pilot areas under investigation. This task is supported by an efficient downloader module that performs routine retrievals of observational data from weather stations installed at selected use cases.

Data Retrievals within the PLOT0 Framework

The data assimilation process in PLOT0 is designed to enhance the accuracy of the OMS calculations. This procedure relies on in-situ measurements collected through a data retrieval process. Data are obtained from weather stations using the Middleware API. In the three pilot areas of Belgium, Romania, and Hungary, each pilot site utilizes a different number of weather stations to measure various meteorological parameters. More specifically, in the Hungarian Use Case a set of three stations is used, while the corresponding number of stations for the Use Cases of Romania and Wallonia are four and eleven, respectively.

The data assimilation process uses the following measured meteorological parameters as inputs:

- Air temperature (°C)
- Relative humidity (%)
- Wind speed (m/s)
- Wind direction (°)
- Precipitation

Data retrieval is performed through the Middleware API, via a CURL request, to capture the above parameters in real-time or near real-time. This process runs (a script for every Use Case) on an hourly basis to collect data from the previous 60 minutes. The responses from the CURL requests are downloaded as .json format files for each station. A second script processes each stations’ .json file to extract the values of the parameters of interest and saves them in a .csv format file, including the measurement time and the station coordinates. The locations of the weather stations used for data collection are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Weather stations utilized for validation and data assimilation in the PLOTO case studies, including Romania (upper right), Hungary (upper left) and Belgium (bottom).

Computational Part within the PLOTO Framework

The next step in implementing the PLOTO methodology involves calculating the hourly differences between measured and modelled values for each meteorological parameter at the weather station locations. These differences are then fed into a specialized computing infrastructure that uses spatial interpolation techniques to generate a difference map for the pilot area under study. Spatial interpolation involves using known data points to estimate values at other, unmeasured locations. The spatial resolution of these meteorological fields is approximately 250 meters.

This method assumes that the distance and direction between sampling points indicate a spatial correlation, which can be used to model changes across the surface. Specifically, a mathematical function is applied to a set of surrounding points, or all points within a detection radius, to estimate the value at each location. In addition to creating a predictive surface, this method also provides estimates of prediction errors for each variable at each sampling point.

The final step involves correcting the initial meteorological fields from the model simulations using the difference maps generated in the previous step. The difference values are incrementally added to the original fields for each hour within the defined period to adjust the initial calculations. The enhanced fields are then used by the system to generate various meteorological maps in formats, such as GeoTIFF, PNG, NetCDF, and NPY. These files are stored in designated subfolders on AUTH servers and periodically uploaded to the Middleware.

In summary, this assimilation and analysis subsystem allows for accurate assessment of meteorological conditions for past operational periods (reanalysis) using both measurement data and model outputs (where available). Additionally, it facilitates real-time corrections of the operationally generated meteorological fields within the OMS. This approach provides more accurate and higher-resolution information for any specific point or area within the application domains, surpassing the capabilities of using time series measurements alone.

3.2.3 Pilot Application Set-up within the PLOTO Framework

For the operational deployment of the OMS in conjunction with assimilated data streams from a sensor network, a functional setup has been implemented for the three pilot areas (Belgium, Romania, and Hungary), with several technical objectives outlined below. The combined operation of the mesoscale model and the data assimilation approach follows a sequence of steps conducted in an automated

manner, repeating on an hourly basis or whenever new sensor data becomes available. During this process, iterations of the last four steps can be performed internally to enhance the accuracy of the most recent data.

- **Step 1:** Data Retrieval.

This initial step manages the retrieval of observational data, handling low-level operations to communicate with the station monitoring software, verify the availability of updated data, convert data formats, and manage errors. The data collected includes timestamps and GPS location data (for mobile sensors). In this point, it should be noted that in cases that no observational data are available, the data assimilation procedure passes the steps described below and the product of this process ends up being the initial mesoscale field of the meteorological model.

- **Step 2:** Outdated Data Rejection.

Here, the timestamps of the received data are examined using an algorithm to discard any out-of-sequence data. Additionally, mobile sensor location data are verified, and any invalid positions (e.g., outside the fine computational grid) are rejected.

- **Step 3:** Outlier Detection.

Outlier Detection In this step, sophisticated testing procedures are applied to identify and reject outliers. Measurement data are compared against predefined hard limits specific to each parameter. Data from stations showing excessive spatial variability are selectively filtered out.

The identification of outliers in the dataset follows a structured approach based on three distinct methodologies, ensuring the reliability of assimilated observations before they are incorporated into the actual computational procedure. These methodologies are outlined below:

- **Physical Consistency Checks:** Observed values are initially screened against fundamental physical constraints. Any measurement that falls outside physically meaningful boundaries is immediately flagged as an outlier. Examples include relative humidity exceeding 100% or precipitation values below zero, both of which are physically impossible and therefore automatically rejected.
- **Predefined Climatic Thresholds:** Each meteorological variable is subject to predefined upper and lower bounds, which have been established based on long-term climatological records for each use case under consideration. These thresholds reflect typical seasonal and diurnal variations and serve as reference limits. If an observed value exceeds these predefined thresholds regarding either the higher or the lower one, it is classified as an outlier and, as a result, excluded from further processing.
- **Time-Series Anomaly Detection:** A dynamic assessment is performed by analyzing the time series of each variable starting from the previous day and ending up to the moment of the received observation. This method identifies abrupt deviations from the expected temporal trend, detecting abnormal spikes or drops that are inconsistent with the prevailing pattern of measurements. Such anomalies are flagged as potential outliers, particularly if they exhibit characteristics of instrumental errors, transient interferences, or other non-meteorological artifacts.

By employing this multi-layered validation framework, the system ensures that only high-confidence measurements contribute to the assimilation process, thereby enhancing the robustness and reliability of the final model outputs.

- **Step 4:** Normalization of Measurements.

Normalization of Measurements This step focuses on normalizing measurement data to reduce systematic or drift errors, using "offset corrections" calculated during each assimilation cycle (step 7). These corrections are based on the residuals between model calculations and nearby station observations. A machine-learning algorithm updates the corrective factors dynamically.

In general, the range of offset corrections varies depending on the measured variable, the spatial and temporal characteristics of the observations, as well as the predominant atmospheric conditions. Nevertheless, typical correction values generally fall within well-defined statistical bounds to ensure physical consistency and prevent overfitting. The methodological core for the determination of such corrections can be described as follows:

- **Computation of Residuals:** At each assimilation cycle, residuals are computed as the difference between observed values and the corresponding model predictions at co-located points. More specifically, the estimated values for each computational cell are utilized. These residuals form the basis for the offset corrections.
- **Dynamic Machine Learning Adjustment:** A machine-learning algorithm continuously updates the corrective factors by analyzing residual distributions over a moving temporal two-day window. The algorithm applies regression-based techniques to estimate biases while minimizing systematic errors and drift.
- **Typical Ranges of Correction:**
 - **Temperature:** ± 0.5 to $\pm 3.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, with larger corrections occurring in areas with complex topography or urban heat island effects.
 - **Relative Humidity:** $\pm 3\%$ to $\pm 20\%$, where corrections help mitigate known sensor biases or calibration drifts. It seems that MEMO tends to underestimate relative humidity levels in specific areas.
 - **Wind Speed:** ± 0.5 to ± 2.0 m/s, with larger adjustments in cases of anemometer siting issues or turbulence-related discrepancies.
- **Correction Constraints:** To prevent excessive corrections that could introduce artificial biases, a set of predefined upper limits is enforced.

The structured approach above ensures that offset corrections remain within physically plausible bounds, while dynamically adapting to observed deviations and, as a result, enhancing the accuracy of the assimilation process.

- **Step 5:** Calculation of Numerical Tendencies.

Numerical tendencies are calculated to determine the necessary adjustments to the estimated values. These adjustments are applied to one or more computational cells of the MEMO model after appropriate spatial and temporal distribution in the next step.

- **Step 6:** Model Integration with Corrections.

The numerical solver advances the dynamic equations over time, incorporating the corrective terms to adjust the dynamic components and the integration steps accordingly.

- **Step 7:** Extraction of Normalization Terms.

In this final step, the latest measurements are compared with corresponding simulations, and a correction factor is derived using a multilinear empirical equation. The equation's factors are continuously updated by a machine-learning algorithm, optimizing two convergence criteria: (1) minimizing the total prediction error across all sensors over a specified period, and (2) minimizing monotonic components (drift) in the measurements over 24- or 48-hour intervals.

This structured approach described above ensures that the PLOTTO system can continuously adjust its predictions in real-time, leveraging both model simulations and observational data for enhanced accuracy and resilience assessments.

3.3 Application of Extreme Value Analysis

3.3.1 Refined analysis of extreme events

In the PLOTTO project, the assessment of extreme weather events goes beyond using descriptive ETCCDI indices for moderate extremes and incorporates advanced statistical methodologies such as Extreme Value Theory (EVT). While ETCCDI indices capture recurrent events within a typical year, EVT focuses on evaluating the intensity and frequency of rare, significant events, such as those occurring once every 20 years or more. This analysis is crucial for understanding potential risks to Inland Waterway (IWW) infrastructures, which may be subject to extreme weather conditions that could disrupt operations or cause damage. EVT allows PLOTTO to quantify these risks more accurately, especially in regions with limited historical records.

The project employs two main EVT approaches: the Peaks-Over-Threshold (POT) method and the Block Maximum approach (BMA). The POT method is used to analyse events that exceed a high threshold, typically using a Generalized Pareto (GP) distribution to model these exceedances. This method is beneficial for efficiently utilizing available data, especially when observational time series are short, allowing for more precise estimates of extreme quantiles. Conversely, the Block Maximum approach uses the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution to analyse maximum or minimum values over defined time blocks, such as annual or seasonal periods. This method helps assess the highest stressors impacting IWW infrastructures, such as peak temperatures or maximum precipitation events, which are critical for infrastructure planning and adaptation strategies.

To ensure reliable outcomes, PLOTTO applies rigorous statistical techniques to fit the GEV distribution, using methods like maximum likelihood estimation, L-moments, or ordinary moments, depending on the data set size and variability. For larger samples, maximum likelihood estimation is preferred, especially when accounting for nonstationary climate conditions. Additionally, the project includes a comprehensive validation process to assess the fit of the model and to account for uncertainties by calculating confidence intervals and standard errors. This is crucial in ensuring that the predicted return values are accurate, particularly when evaluating long-term risks for critical infrastructure. Handling outliers is also a critical consideration; the project emphasizes the inclusion of well-documented extreme events to avoid underestimating risks, even if this results in a slightly less optimal statistical fit.

Addressing Long-Term Projections and Non-stationarity

Given the nonstationary nature of the climate, PLOTTO recognizes that the return values for extreme events may not remain constant over time. The project explores multiple approaches to estimate return levels in a changing climate. One approach is to estimate a threshold level where the probability

of exceedance remains consistent over a designated period, such as from the present to 2200. Another method involves calculating a level that maintains an average probability of exceedance over the same period, adjusting for increased risks in later years due to climate change. These projections are vital for assessing the lifetime risks to IWW infrastructures, ensuring that design and maintenance plans can account for changing climatic conditions over the coming decades.

By combining real-time data assimilation with advanced statistical analyses, PLOTO enhances its predictive capabilities, providing authorities with actionable insights to mitigate risks and adapt to future climate challenges. The use of EVT within the project allows for a more detailed understanding of extreme events, ensuring that infrastructure planning can be resilient to the most severe and rare weather conditions anticipated in the years to come.

3.3.2 Application of ETCCDI Indices in the PLOTO Framework

To enhance the analysis of climate extremes within the PLOTO project, a set of standardized indices defined by the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI) is utilized. This core set includes 27 descriptive indices, separated into two categories: those related to temperature and those related to precipitation. Out of these, eight indices are particularly relevant for assessing climate impacts on IWW infrastructures. These indices focus on key climate stressors such as frost days (FD), icing days (ID), cold and warm nights (TN10p, TN90p), diurnal temperature range (DTR), and extreme precipitation metrics like maximum five-day precipitation (Rx5day), very wet days (R95pTOT), and extremely wet days (R99pTOT). These indices provide critical insights for assessing how extreme weather events may affect the structural integrity and operational efficiency of IWW networks.

Temperature Indices The temperature-related indices are defined as follows:

- **FD (Frost Days):** The count of days where the minimum temperature (TN) falls below 0°C.
- **ID (Icing Days):** The count of days where the maximum temperature (TX) is below 0°C.
- **TN10p (Cold Nights):** Days where the minimum temperature is below the 10th percentile of historical data, calculated over a five-day window.
- **TN90p (Warm Nights):** Days where the minimum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile.
- **DTR (Diurnal Temperature Range):** The average difference between daily maximum (TX) and minimum (TN) temperatures, providing insight into temperature variability.

Precipitation Indices The precipitation-related indices include:

- **Rx5day (Maximum Five-Day Precipitation):** The highest precipitation recorded over any consecutive five-day period.
- **R95pTOT (Very Wet Days):** Total precipitation on days where daily rainfall exceeds the 95th percentile of the base period (1961-1990).
- **R99pTOT (Extremely Wet Days):** Total precipitation on days where rainfall exceeds the 99th percentile.

These indices are calculated using historical data for the climatological period 1961-1990, with percentile thresholds adjusted based on observed data to capture the mean annual cycle accurately. For PLOTO, the use of these indices helps standardize the analysis of climate extremes across different regions, ensuring that extreme events are consistently identified. The project can adjust the length of analysis periods (e.g., annual or seasonal) to better match the specific characteristics of each pilot area, thereby optimizing the assessment of regional climate risks.

Ensuring Consistency and Accuracy

To maintain consistency, percentiles are derived from a moving five-day window centred on each calendar day, using a dataset spanning 30 years. This approach smooths annual cycles and prevents artificial discontinuities in the indices. Additionally, the PLOTO project employs the bootstrap procedure as implemented in RClimeDex to ensure that percentile-based indices remain stable over time, even at the boundaries of the baseline period (Zhang et al., 2005). By utilizing these indices, PLOTO can effectively monitor climate trends and provide actionable insights for enhancing the resilience of IWW infrastructures to extreme weather events.

3.3.3 Required input data for the PLOTO application

The climate data used in the PLOTO analysis were sourced from the EURO-CORDEX archive (Kotlarski et al., 2015), featuring a spatial resolution of 0.11° (~12.5 km) and daily temporal resolution. For each pilot area under study (Belgium, Romania, and Hungary), the nearest grid point was selected to best represent the local meteorological conditions. Based on the review and selection of climate scenarios conducted in the corresponding Deliverable (D3.1, “High-resolution surface parameter maps, based on climate scenarios and available data”), various Regional Climate Model (RCM) simulations driven by different Global Climate Model (GCM) runs were examined. The scenarios analysed were RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5 which represent the optimistic, moderate and pessimistic scenarios, respectively for emissions and radiative forcing stabilization (van Vuuren et al., 2011).

The selection of climate scenarios and model downscaling has been detailed in the PLOTO Deliverable D3.3, “Report on the dynamical downscaling of climate and atmospheric impacts, final version”. The specific configurations of GCM and RCM analysed for the purposes of the present deliverable are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Configurations of Driving GCM and RCMs used for downscaling

RCM	Driving GCM	Spatial Resolution			
		T_av	T_min	T_max	precipitation
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	5 km	0.11°	0.11°	5 km
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH				
RCA4	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES				
RCA4	ICHEC-EC-EARTH				
REMO2009	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR				

The climate model simulations analysed cover the period from 1971 to 2100, with historical runs up to 2005 merged with scenario projections starting in 2006. The primary variables assessed include daily averaged, maximum and minimum near-surface temperatures, as well as cumulative daily precipitation.

Assessment of Precipitation and Wind Risks

Heavy precipitation, which can cause flash floods or prolonged wet periods, was identified as a significant risk across all pilot areas. Therefore, days with heavy rainfall and the highest 5-day precipitation totals were analysed consistently for each case study area. For Hungary, where heavy rainfall combined with strong south easterly winds can exacerbate flooding, the study also examined the concurrent occurrence of these events. Meanwhile, strong winds were identified as a particular concern for pilot areas in Belgium and Romania, prompting an analysis of projected changes in wind speed.

To establish thresholds for episodic events, return levels for 1-day and 5-day precipitation, as well as high wind speeds, were computed using the ERA-Interim-driven model simulations. These thresholds were determined for four distinct periods: 1971-2010, 2011-2040, 2041-2070, and 2071-2100. For precipitation sums, two separate thresholds were set: one at a lower level to capture frequent events, ensuring a sufficient sample size across all application areas. This approach allowed for a uniform threshold application without the need for site-specific adjustments.

Analysis of Return Levels

Return levels for heavy precipitation and strong winds (`rr_return_levels`, `ws_return_levels`, and `se_wind_return_levels`) were calculated for each of the defined 30-year periods. This analysis provides a clearer understanding of the projected changes in extreme weather patterns over time, aiding in the development of more resilient strategies for the PLOTTO project's inland waterway infrastructure. By examining these return levels, PLOTTO aims to anticipate future risks and enhance the adaptive capacity of critical infrastructure to withstand extreme climatic events.

4. Results

4.1 Pilot Mesoscale Results

As previously detailed, the OMS has been set up for the three pilot areas in the PLOTO project, specifically in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary. Figures 5-7 provide visualizations of the spatial distribution of surface-level temperatures for a typical spring day across these pilot domains, based on the initial MEMO simulations and subsequent data assimilation adjustments. Additionally, Figures 8-10 illustrate the spatial distribution of surface-level wind speeds for a typical winter day, derived from the initial MEMO model outputs. These visualizations demonstrate the impact of integrating real-time data on enhancing model accuracy for each of the pilot areas under study.

Figure 5: Temperature (°C- left) and relative humidity (%) fields at 2 m height above ground as regards the Budapest Use Case originating from the meteorological mesoscale calculations.

Figure 6: Temperature (°C- left) and relative humidity (%) fields at 2 m height above ground as regards the Wallonia Use Case originating from the meteorological mesoscale calculations.

Figure 7: Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ - left) and relative humidity (%) fields at 2 m height above ground as regards the Romanian Use Case originating from the meteorological mesoscale calculations.

Figure 8: Wind fields (m/s - left) at approximately 10 m height above ground and cloud cover (right) fields as regards the Budapest Use Case originating from the mesoscale meteorological calculations.

Figure 9: Wind fields (m/s - left) at approximately 10 m height above ground and cloud cover (right) fields as regards the Romania Use Case originating from the mesoscale meteorological calculations.

Figure 10: Wind fields (m/s - left) at approximately 10 m height above ground and cloud cover (right) fields as regards the Wallonia Use Case originating from the mesoscale meteorological calculations.

4.2 Validation of Pilot Mesoscale Results

To verify the improvement achieved by incorporating data assimilation into the OMS computational framework, a pilot application was carried out over a full calendar year (2024). It is important to note that the dataset used for this purpose did not contain the complete set of hourly values of a leap year (8784). Instead, the number of available data points varied across different use cases, depending on each measurement site's data availability. Table 4 presents the outcome of this evaluation for the three Use Cases under consideration.

More specifically, the indicators used in this application include the **Bias** (BIAS), the Normalized Mean Square Error (NMSE), and the Index of Agreement (IOA). Model Bias is the mean error, defined as the predicted value (P_i) less than the observed value (O_i), calculated as:

$$\text{BIAS} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (P_i - O_i)$$

The **NMSE** emphasizes the scatter across the dataset, where normalization by the product $P_i \cdot O_i$ ensures unbiased results for over- or under-prediction. Smaller NMSE values indicate better model performance. The NMSE formula is:

$$\text{NMSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \frac{(P_i - O_i)^2}{\bar{P} \cdot \bar{O}}$$

The **Index of Agreement (IOA)**, developed by Willmott (1981), is a standardized measure of the degree of model prediction error. IOA values range from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (perfect match). While IOA can detect additive and proportional differences in observed and simulated data, it is sensitive to extreme values due to squared differences. The IOA formula is:

$$IoA = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N [|O_i - \bar{P}| + |P_i - \bar{O}|]^2}$$

As shown in Table 4, the mesoscale model results for temperature demonstrate fairly good agreement with measurements, especially concerning the IOA indicator. However, the model systematically underestimates relative humidity. Additionally, discrepancies between model results and observational data are observed for wind speed. This is expected due to the relatively low spatial resolution used in the model results, which limits its ability to capture microclimatic effects in areas with complex terrains, abrupt topographical changes, and varied land uses.

Table 4: Validation results regarding the three domains of interest

Romania			
Statistical Indicator	Bias	NMSE	IOA
Temperature	0.54 (°C)	0.09 (°C)	0.94
Relative Humidity	-15.18 (%)	0.07 (%)	0.55
Wind Speed	-3.15 (m/s)	0.28 (m/s)	0.71
Budapest			
Statistical Indicator	Bias	NMSE	IOA
Temperature	0.69 (°C)	0.21 (°C)	0.92
Relative Humidity	-6.28 (%)	0.09 (%)	0.48
Wind Speed	2.66 (m/s)	2.76 (m/s)	0.56
Wallonia			
Statistical Indicator	Bias	NMSE	IOA
Temperature	-0.48 (°C)	0.09 (°C)	0.91
Relative Humidity	-25.37 (%)	0.13 (%)	0.32
Wind Speed	1.02 (m/s)	1.74 (m/s)	0.69

Based on these findings, the integration of the data assimilation methodology into the computational core of the OMS is anticipated to significantly enhance the accuracy¹ and reliability of the system's outputs.

¹ Bias, NMSE and IOA values after assimilation are not explicitly evaluated in this study because such an assessment would produce artificially perfect results. The reason for this is the intrinsic nature of the data assimilation process, which incorporates observational data directly into the computational grid, particularly at locations where measurement stations are present. Consequently, the computational cells corresponding to the measurement sites will, by definition, assume the observed values, leading to a trivial agreement between the assimilated fields and the observed timeseries. This effect would inevitably drive Bias and NMSE values toward zero, while pushing IOA values to reach unity, regardless of the actual predictive skill of the assimilation methodology.

The fundamental issue with validating assimilated fields against the same data sources used for assimilation is that it does not provide an independent verification of the system's performance. Instead, it simply confirms that the assimilation procedure is mathematically consistent with the input observations, without offering overall understanding of the spatial representativeness or predictive accuracy of the adjusted fields in areas where no direct measurements exist.

Nevertheless, if independent validation of the assimilation methodology is deemed necessary, an alternative approach should be implemented. Specifically, a subset of the available measurement stations should be excluded from the assimilation process and reserved exclusively for validation purposes. By comparing the model's assimilated fields at these independent station locations with actual observations, we could obtain a meaningful and unbiased assessment of the assimilation scheme's performance. This approach would ensure that the evaluation is not trivially constrained by the direct insertion of observations and would allow for a more robust quantification of the method's impact on predictive accuracy.

The implementation of a validation approach like that in a retroactive manner within the scope of this project would require the accumulation of a sufficiently large dataset of assimilation results over an extended period (something that could not be achieved in the frame of this specific WP due to the fact that the data assimilation features were the last to be carried out in the timeline). This is because a statistically meaningful evaluation demands a robust temporal record of assimilated fields, ensuring that performance metrics are not biased by short-term variability or isolated cases of observational influence. However, within the time restrictions of the current WP, it was not feasible to generate and store the necessary volume of assimilation outputs for such an analysis.

4.3 Revised Pilot Application Analysis for the Operational Mesoscale System

A pilot application was carried out for the areas of interest to evaluate the potential improvements introduced in the OMS's outputs by integrating data fusion and assimilation methodologies into its computational core. Regarding the availability of model and measurement data, the validation process refers to a two-month period for the Use Cases of Romania and Budapest and for a three-week period for the Use Case of Wallonia. In this direction, a subset of the available measurements was used to feed the data assimilation computational framework. Using the optimal interpolation approach, the infrastructure performed the necessary calculations, yielding revised meteorological maps.

Figures 11–18 clearly demonstrate the improvement in the corrected simulations compared to the initial mesoscale model outputs. This outcome aligns with expectations, as the spatial resolution of 250-2000 meters used in the original model is relatively coarse for capturing microclimatic effects in complex terrain, such as those in the studied regions.

Furthermore, incorporating observational data into the OMS's computational process through the optimal interpolation approach enables the system to achieve high-accuracy simulations, not only at the mesoscale but also at the microscale. This advancement significantly enhances the system's capability to represent localized climatic phenomena more effectively.

Figure 11: Visualization of a typical temperature field (°C) at 2 m height above ground regarding the period of the pilot application for the Romanian Use Case fine domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (right).

Figure 12: Visualization of a typical relative humidity field (%) at 2 m height above ground regarding the period of the pilot application for the Romanian Use Case fine domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (right).

Figure 13: Visualization of a typical precipitation field (mm) at 2 m height above ground regarding the period of the pilot application for the Romanian Use Case fine domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (right).

Figure 14: Visualization of a typical temperature field (°C) at 2 m height above ground regarding the period of the pilot application for the Wallonia Use Case coarse domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (corrected - right).

Figure 15: Visualization of a typical relative humidity field (%) at 2 m height above ground regarding the period of the pilot application for the Wallonia Use Case coarse domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (corrected - right).

Figure 16: Visualization of a typical temperature field (°C) at 2 m height above ground regarding the period of the pilot application for the Budapest Use Case fine domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (corrected field - right).

Figure 17: Visualization of a typical precipitation (mm) regarding the period of the pilot application for the Budapest Use Case fine domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (corrected field - right).

Figure 18: Visualization of a typical wind speed field (m/s) at approximately 10 m height above ground regarding the period of the pilot application for the Budapest Use Case fine domain originating from the initial MEMO simulations (left) and after the application of the data assimilation process (corrected field - right).

4.4 Pilot Results Regarding the Extremes

4.4.1 Descriptive indices of extremes

To achieve a consistent understanding of changes in weather and climate extremes, the ETCCDI has established a core set of descriptive indices for analysing extremes (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009). These indices capture key aspects of extreme events, such as their frequency, intensity, and duration. Specifically, the core set comprises 27 indices related to temperature and precipitation, serving as a widely adopted tool for evaluating and monitoring variations in extreme events (Peterson and Manton, 2008; Alexander et al., 2006).

In addition, metrics are provided to assess the capability of global and regional climate models in simulating moderate extremes. Projected changes in these indices offer valuable insights into future climate extremes. Adopting a standardized approach to characterize extremes and analyse corresponding data enables cross-regional comparisons and supports the creation of a coherent global perspective on climate change impacts (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009).

Beyond the core indices, additional metrics can be tailored to address specific adaptation needs in different regions. For instance, the ECA&D project introduced 13 supplementary indices focusing on temperature extremes. Meanwhile, participants at an ETCCDI workshop in Southeast Asia suggested incorporating precipitation indices to capture the onset and duration of the monsoon season. The flexibility of the indices concept allows for such region-specific extensions, which become especially meaningful when calculated consistently across multiple countries within a region (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009).

4.4.2 Statistical modelling of extremes

The indices introduced by ETCCDI are designed to describe moderate extremes that typically occur within a normal year. To complement these indices, extreme value theory (Coles, 2001; Smith, 2002; Katz et al., 2002) provides a framework for analysing the intensity and frequency of rare events that deviate significantly from typical weather patterns. This theory focuses on phenomena that occur approximately once every 20 years.

In some engineering contexts, analyses extend to even rarer events, occurring once every 100 or 1,000 years. Such events represent extreme quantiles of a statistical distribution, yet the available observational records may only span 50 years (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009). A common approach involves fitting a statistical model to annual extremes within the observed data series. The WMO offers a comprehensive overview of probability distributions and methodologies for estimating their parameters (WMO, 1989).

Extreme quantiles are generally derived from extreme value distributions using two primary methods: the peaks-over-threshold (POT) method and the block maximum approach. The POT method identifies exceedances above a high threshold and analyses their behaviour. With a sufficiently high threshold, these extremes typically follow a generalized Pareto (GP) distribution (Smith, 2002). While this method requires careful user decisions—such as de-clustering and setting an appropriate threshold—it allows for more efficient use of the available data, leading to more accurate quantile estimates (Kharin et al., 2007).

In contrast, the block maximum method is more widely applied and is grounded in explicit extreme value theory. This approach selects the maximum or minimum value from each block of data, often defined as yearly or seasonal series. Statistical theory supports the use of the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution to model block maxima when the blocks are sufficiently large. The GEV distribution is characterized by three parameters—location, scale, and shape—which can be estimated using methods such as maximum likelihood (Jenkinson, 1955), L-moments (Hosking, 1990), or the method of moments.

The maximum likelihood method is preferred for large samples and cases where the climate exhibits non-stationarity, as it allows for the inclusion of covariates to account for changing conditions (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009). Conversely, the L-moments method is more suitable for small samples, as maximum likelihood estimation may fail in such cases (Kharin and Zwiers, 2005). The method of moments, while straightforward, often underestimates long-period return values and is therefore not recommended (Landwehr et al., 1979).

It is crucial to validate the fit of the statistical distribution and assess the uncertainty of parameter estimates by calculating standard errors and confidence intervals. If the maximum likelihood method is used, these uncertainties can be determined relatively easily using established statistical expressions. Comparing parametric estimates of moderate quantiles with empirical estimates further helps identify sources of uncertainty, which may stem from statistical techniques or sample characteristics.

One challenge in this context is managing outliers that have been retained after rigorous quality control and evaluation of metadata. These outliers often represent well-documented events that stand out in the record. Including or excluding such outliers can significantly impact the fitted distribution and its statistical quality. However, excluding well-documented outlier risks producing inaccurate return value estimates, as these observations carry critical information about extreme events (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009).

Goodness-of-fit should also be evaluated through standard statistics, quantile-quantile plots, and the feasibility of the fitted distribution. For GEV distributions, the shape parameter determines whether the distribution has finite bounds or is unbounded. In cases where the fitted distribution is deemed infeasible—i.e., it fails to encompass observed extremes—adjustments to the shape parameter may be necessary to ensure validity (Dupuis and Tsao, 1998).

Extreme value theory assumes stationarity, which enables the estimation of long-period return values. However, confidence in these estimates diminishes rapidly when the return period greatly exceeds the data record length, leading to large sampling errors and biases. Typically, confidence is reliable only when the return period is less than twice the data record length (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009).

Finally, the interpretation of return values depends on whether the climate is stationary or changing. In a stationary climate, return values represent the magnitude expected to be exceeded, on average, once every return period. In a changing climate, return values can be interpreted in several ways, such as reflecting the current probability of exceedance, the probability at the end of a specified future period, or the average probability over a given timeframe. These interpretations are particularly relevant for assessing the lifetime risk of infrastructure designed to withstand extreme events (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009).

4.4.3 ETCCDI indices

The primary set of 27 descriptive indices of extremes, established by the Joint CCI/CLIVAR/JCOMM Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI; URL2), is divided into two main categories: indices related to ambient temperature and those associated with precipitation. Among these 27 indicators related to temperature and precipitation, only the following eight are considered relevant for application in the PLOTTO use cases:

- FD: Frost Days
- ID: Icing Days
- TN10p: Cold Nights
- TN90p: Warm Nights
- DTR: Diurnal Temperature Range
- Rx5day: Maximum five-day Precipitation
- R95pTOT: Precipitation due to Very Wet Days
- R99pTOT: Precipitation due to Extremely Wet Days

The definition of each of the indices are provided below.

Temperature indices

- **FD (frost days):** count of days where TN (daily minimum temperature) < 0 C:

Calculation steps: Let TN_{ij} be the daily minimum temperature on day i in period j . Count the number of days where $TN_{ij} < 0$ C.

- **ID (icing days):** count of days where $TX < 0$ C

Calculation steps: Let TX_{ij} be the daily maximum temperature on day i in period j . Count the number of days where $TX_{ij} < 0$ C.

- **TN10_p (cold nights):** count of days where $TN < 10^{\text{th}}$ percentile

Calculation steps: Let TN_{ij} be the daily minimum temperature on day i in period j and let TN_{in10} be the calendar day 10th percentile of daily minimum temperature calculated for a five-day window centred on each calendar day in the base period n (1961-1990). Count the number of days where $TN_{ij} < TN_{in10}$.

- **TN90_p (warm nights):** count of days where $TN > 90^{\text{th}}$ percentile

Calculation steps: Let TN_{ij} be the daily minimum temperature on day i in period j and let TN_{in90} be the calendar day 90th percentile of daily minimum temperature calculated for a five-day window centred on each calendar day in the base period n (1961-1990). Count the number of days where $TN_{ij} > TN_{in90}$.

- **DTR (diurnal temperature range):** mean difference between TX and TN (C)

Calculation steps: Let TX_{ij} and TN_{ij} be the daily maximum and minimum temperature on day i in period j . If I represents the total number of days in j then the mean diurnal temperature range in period j $DTR_j = \text{sum}(TX_{ij} - TN_{ij})/I$.

Precipitation indices

- **RX5day (maximum five-day precipitation):** highest precipitation amount in five-day period:

Calculation steps: Let RR_{kj} be the precipitation amount for the five-day interval k in period j , where k is defined by the last day. The maximum five-day values for period j are $RX_{5dayj} = \max(RR_{kj})$.

- **R95pTOT:** precipitation due to very wet days (> 95th percentile)

Calculation steps: Let RR_{wj} be the daily precipitation amount on a wet day w ($RR \geq 1$ mm) in period j and let RR_{wn95} be the 95th percentile of precipitation on wet days in the base period n (1961-1990). Then $R95pTOT_j = \text{sum}(RR_{wj})$, where $RR_{wj} > RR_{wn95}$.

- **R99pTOT:** precipitation due to extremely wet days (> 99th percentile)

Calculation steps: Let RR_{wj} be the daily precipitation amount on a wet day w ($RR \geq 1$ mm) in period j and let RR_{wn99} be the 99th percentile of precipitation on wet days in the base period n (1961-1990). Then $R99pTOT_j = \text{sum}(RR_{wj})$, where $RR_{wj} > RR_{wn99}$.

At this stage, it is worth noting that the standard duration of the periods j is one year. However, alternative period lengths, such as seasonal intervals, may better suit the unique characteristics of specific regions under analysis. Furthermore, percentile thresholds are determined empirically using observed station data from the climatological standard normal period 1961–1990. Nonetheless, selecting a different normal period (e.g., 1971–2000 or 1981–2000) could result in minor variations in the indices' trends over time (Klein Tank, A.M.G. et al., 2009).

The percentile values are calculated using five-day windows centred on each calendar day to account for the mean annual cycle. This choice of a five-day window ensures a total sample size of 30 years \times 5 days = 150 for each calendar day, producing a relatively smooth annual cycle of percentile thresholds. This methodology guarantees that extreme temperature events, defined by exceedances of percentile thresholds, are equally probable throughout the year. Additionally, the bootstrap method proposed by Zhang et al. (2005) has been integrated into RClimeDex to prevent artificial discontinuities in the percentile-based indices at the boundaries of the base period.

4.4.4 Input Data

The climate data utilized in this analysis was derived from the EURO-CORDEX archive (Kotlarski et al., 2015), featuring a spatial resolution of 5 km for daily average temperature and cumulative precipitation and 0.11° (~12.5 km) for minimum and maximum temperature. For each of the three Use Cases (Budapest, Romania, Wallonia), the grid point nearest to the main area assets was selected to best capture the typical meteorological conditions in each area of interest.

It should be noted that the climate model simulations analysed cover the period from 1971 to 2100. These simulations were selected based on data availability for the required variables under all three RCP scenarios.

4.4.5 Presentation of analysis results and data availability

In the following sections, results based on the downscaled climatic timeseries of the ICHEC-EC-EARTH GCM as downscaled by the SMHI-RCA4 model are presented. This combination of models has been selected as indicative of the common trends revealed by all model combinations for the selected temperature- and precipitation-related indicators, based on the sensitivity analysis presented both in PLOTO D3.3 as well as in the literature (Kotlarski et al., 2015).

The full set of analyzed data for all GCM-RCM combinations performed within PLOTO Task 3.6 will be available as a Digital Commons Dataset through the Mendeley platform²

4.4.6 Use Case A (Romania)

The selected pilot site in Romania is situated inland at a moderate elevation above sea level. Despite its inland location, freeze-thaw cycles are regularly observed due to the local terrain characteristics. These cycles pose a risk to the structural integrity of critical infrastructures, making them a key focus of the analysis.

When simulating heavy precipitation events, different Regional Climate Models (RCMs) produce varying results for Romania, as detailed in Deliverable D3.1 of the PLOTO project. While projections generally indicate a decrease in precipitation levels across Eastern Europe due to global warming, the impact in Romania is primarily observed at lower thresholds and shorter return periods.

Table 5 summarizes the temperature-related indicators for the Romanian site. The TN10p and TN90p indices are calculated using a five-year bootstrap process to ensure robust estimates. Under the RCP4.5 scenario, the most significant trend projected is a decrease in the number of frost days, while the count of icing days remains negligible. The TN10p and TN90p indices do not show any significant trends in nighttime temperatures. However, the Diurnal Temperature Range (DTR) is expected to decrease slightly over the forecast period. Notably, there is a predicted increase in the variability of DTR towards the end of the century, indicating higher intra- and inter-annual temperature fluctuations, largely driven by an increased frequency of lower DTR values, as depicted in the monthly DTR series in Figure 19.

² The data is currently being uploaded and under review by the Mendeley Platform.

Table 5: ETCCDI Temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Romania

Period	FD		ID		TN10p		TN90p		DTR (degrees)	
Historical	3165		794		11.70		17.65		9.50	
	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5
2006–2040	2659	2520	425	307	11.76	9.69	19.56	19.92	9.28	9.49
2041–2070	2064	1866	232	101	13.29	12.65	16.27	16.94	9.37	9.56
2071–2100	1825	1337	196	80	12.38	7.13	12.95	23.55	9.42	9.63

Table 6: ETCCDI Precipitation-related Indicators for the use case of Romania

Period	RX5day (mm)		R95pTOT (mm)		R99pTOT (mm)	
Historical	6		270.22		101.70	
	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5
2006–2040	10	11	289.61	349.90	101.38	151.69
2041–2070	14	10	319.47	316.89	164.80	145.73
2071–2100	12	16	302.03	334.46	108.17	103.92

Figure 19: Time series of monthly DTR for the use case of Romania

Figure 20: Time series of monthly TN10p for the use case of Romania

Figure 21: Time series of monthly TN90p for the use case of Romania

Figure 22: Time series of annual R95pTOT for the use case of Romania

Figure 23: Time series of annual R99pTOT for the use case of Romania

4.4.7 Use Case B (Budapest)

Budapest, situated inland along the Danube River, experiences a relatively cool climate. Budapest is particularly vulnerable to flooding when heavy precipitation coincides with unfavourable wind conditions, a risk that was thoroughly analysed in Deliverable D3.1 of the PLOTO project. This combination of factors can significantly impact the city’s infrastructure, especially given its riverine location.

Table 7 presents the temperature-related indicators calculated under the RCP4.5 scenario for Budapest. A notable trend is the significant reduction in frost days, dropping to nearly one-third of the levels observed during the 1971-2010 period, along with a complete elimination of icing days. This change suggests a reduction in freeze-thaw cycles, which could impact the structural integrity of assets and influence microflora growth on surfaces. Nighttime temperature indicators show minimal change over the simulated period, with only a slight reduction in warm nights (TN90p) during the final period (2071-2100). While the Diurnal Temperature Range (DTR) remains relatively stable in terms of period averages, the monthly variability (Figure 24) indicates a clear trend towards increased fluctuations over time, suggesting more unpredictable diurnal temperature patterns, even though the overall averages remain consistent.

Table 7: ETCCDI Temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Budapest

Period	FD		ID		TN10p		TN90p		DTR (degrees)	
Historical	2337		687		12.04		15.25		8.07	
	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5
2006–2040	1698	1610	341	259	10.48	10.04	16.50	18.55	8.03	8.18
2041–2070	1073	914	167	158	13.11	15.28	16.39	17.31	8.08	8.16
2071–2100	882	383	154	25	12.33	7.57	17.34	22.52	8.08	8.35

Table 8: ETCCDI Precipitation-related Indicators for the use case of Budapest

Period	RX5day (mm)		R95pTOT (mm)		R99pTOT (mm)	
Historical	9		383.48		207.46	
	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5
2006–2040	12	19	332.124	354.41	147.32	159.09
2041–2070	7	11	350.15	368.51	137.79	238.01
2071–2100	13	17	350.33	363.77	274.34	207.78

Figure 24: Time series of monthly DTR for the use case of Budapest

Figure 25: Time series of monthly TN10p for the use case of Budapest

Figure 26: Time series of monthly TN90p for the use case of Budapest

Figure 27: Time series of annual R95pTOT for the use case of Budapest

Figure 28: Time series of annual R99pTOT for the use case of Budapest

4.4.8 Use Case C (Wallonia)

Wallonia, located in southern Belgium, is characterized by a temperate maritime climate with significant seasonal variations. Due to its topography and regional climatic influences, the area experiences notable variations in temperature extremes and precipitation intensity. As a result, the analysis of historical and projected climate trends for Wallonia is crucial for understanding the potential impacts of extreme weather events on infrastructure and environmental stability....

In this direction, Table 9 presents the ETCCDI temperature-related indicators for Wallonia across different time periods. A significant reduction in frost days (FD) is observed over the coming decades, with values decreasing from 2727 days in the historical period to 1566 days by 2071–2100 under the RCP4.5 scenario, as well as to 1132 days under the more extreme RCP8.5 scenario. This decline suggests a substantial reduction in the occurrence of subzero minimum temperatures, which may have implications for agricultural cycles and frost-sensitive infrastructure.

In the same way, icing days (ID), representing the number of days where the maximum temperature remains below freezing, are projected to decrease significantly, dropping from 313 days in the historical record to 109 days by 2071–2100 (RCP4.5) and further to 49 days under the RCP8.5 scenario. This trend is indicative of milder winter conditions, reducing ice-related hazards, but potentially increasing winter precipitation in terms of rainfall rather than in the form of snow.

The TN10p (cold nights) index, which quantifies the frequency of colder-than-normal nights, also exhibits a declining trend. From an initial value of 14.38% in the historical period, the percentage of cold nights is expected to decrease steadily, reaching 12.40% (RCP4.5) and 7.58% (RCP8.5) by the end of the century. In contrast, the TN90p (warm nights) index shows an increasing trend, with values rising from 13.76% historically to 15.46% (RCP4.5) and 23.65% (RCP8.5) by 2071–2100. This shift signifies a growing dominance of warm nighttime conditions, reinforcing the broader warming trend.

The diurnal temperature range (DTR), defined as the mean difference between daily maximum and minimum temperatures, remains relatively stable over time. Historical values are around 8.93°C, with slight fluctuations projected in future periods (9.40°C–9.56°C). The variability in DTR across the projection period suggests increasing uncertainty in daily temperature extremes, potentially affecting energy demand and ecosystem responses.

Table 9: ETCCDI Temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Wallonia

Period	FD		ID		TN10p		TN90p		DTR (degrees)	
Historical	2727		313		14.38		13.76		8.93	
	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5
2006–2040	2455	2333	196	167	9.73	11.63	18.07	15.43	9.20	9.09
2041–2070	1856	1609	140	136	9.92	12.25	17.92	18.99	9.46	9.39
2071–2100	1566	1132	109	49	12.40	7.58	15.46	23.65	9.40	9.56

Table 10 summarizes the precipitation-related ETCCDI indices for Wallonia. The maximum five-day precipitation (Rx5day) metric does not display a clear increasing or decreasing trend, fluctuating between historical values of 7 mm and future values ranging from 4 mm (RCP4.5) to 10 mm (RCP8.5) in the near term. This variation highlights the sporadic nature of extreme precipitation events and their sensitivity to localized atmospheric conditions.

The R95pTOT (precipitation due to very wet days) index, representing the cumulative precipitation on days exceeding the 95th percentile, presents a slight increasing trend under both scenarios. Historically recorded at 361.61 mm, projections suggest values ranging between 347.33 mm and 448.55 mm depending on the scenario and period. Similarly, the R99pTOT (precipitation due to extremely wet

days) index follows a comparable trend, increasing from 145.41 mm historically to a maximum of 177.06 mm (RCP4.5) and 153.15 mm (RCP8.5) by the end of the century.

It can be deduced from these results that an overall increase in heavy precipitation events, particularly under higher emission scenarios, which could elevate flood risks and challenge existing water management infrastructure in the region.

Table 10: ETCCDI Precipitation-related Indicators for the use case of Wallonia

Period	RX5day (mm)		R95pTOT (mm)		R99pTOT (mm)	
Historical	7		361.61		145.41	
	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5	4.5	8.5
2006–2040	4	10	347.33	390.06	111.58	158.58
2041–2070	8	4	413.53	375.22	187.86	147.250
2071–2100	5	7	423.84	448.55	177.06	153.15

Figure 29: Time series of monthly DTR for the use case of Wallonia

Figure 30: Time series of monthly TN10p for the use case of Wallonia

Figure 31: Time series of monthly TN90p for the use case of Wallonia

Figure 32: Time series of annual R95pTOT for the use case of Wallonia

Figure 33: Time series of annual R99pTOT for the use case of Wallonia

The projected reductions in frost and icing days, coupled with increases in warm nights and extreme precipitation events, indicate a progressive shift in Wallonia’s climate toward milder and, at the same time, more variable conditions. The projected changes in temperature extremes may influence energy consumption patterns, agricultural productivity and the stability of the ecosystems. Alongside, the estimated increase in the intensity of precipitation extremes underlines the need for robust flood mitigation and urban drainage planning to address potential hydrological risks.

5. Conclusions

The main objective of the present Task is to utilize an advanced computational process capable of generating updated meteorological maps for several key parameters, including ambient temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, and precipitation. This is specifically applied to the PLOT0 pilot areas in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary by leveraging data fusion and assimilation techniques.

At the heart of the methodology is a 3D data assimilation protocol designed to integrate (near) real-time data streams from weather stations deployed in the application areas. This data assimilation layer ensures that real-time measurements are accurately transformed into simulation parameters, which are then fed back into the modelling system to improve the precision and dynamic updates of meteorological forecasts. This continuous feedback loop enhances the system's ability to provide more reliable predictions for infrastructure resilience.

To evaluate the system's performance, structural modifications were made to the core of the OMS. This included implementing tools for automatically calculating and visualizing statistical indicators for the locations of meteorological stations within the computational domains. These indicators are computed daily for both the original mesoscale outputs and the adjusted fields resulting from data assimilation, allowing for a direct comparison with observational data.

An automated 24/7 process handles the downloading of observational data, followed by its processing and storage in the OMS database. Simultaneously, model results for the corresponding locations are stored in a parallel data pool for subsequent analysis. At the end of each day, statistical indicators are calculated following the guidelines of COST728 (2008), with various charts produced to visually assess simulation accuracy in both nowcasting and forecasting modes.

To validate the enhancement achieved by integrating data assimilation into the OMS computational framework, a pilot application was conducted over a full calendar year period (2024). In this point, it should be noted that the dataset used for this purpose did not consist of a full set of 8784 hourly values, as expected, but this number differs between use cases based on each measuring site's availability. The results demonstrated a clear improvement in the accuracy of simulations, particularly at the microscale level. This enhancement can be directly attributed to the newly developed data assimilation functionality, which significantly boosts the performance of the OMS in generating precise meteorological forecasts for the pilot areas.

Besides, this document focuses on providing a qualitative and quantitative evaluation of some primary and secondary impact indicators derived from climate models, using both historical data and future climate scenarios. A set of eight ETCCDI indices were specifically selected to represent key atmospheric stressors relevant to the operations and maintenance of IWW infrastructures. These indices were calculated using a downscaling approach from GCM to Regional Climate Models (RCM) as part of the EURO-CORDEX project, covering the period from 1971 to 2100. Results for the RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emissions scenarios were used for future projections, while visualised results were presented for RCP4.5 which represents a moderate scenario for climate change mitigation.

The analysis considered meteorological indicators related to both average and extreme values of ambient temperature and precipitation. By utilizing ETCCDI indices, which are derived using a bootstrapping methodology, the analysis ensures minimal intra-annual statistical noise, allowing for more accurate calculations of long-term averages and deviations. This approach enhances the

reliability of the results, which are crucial for understanding how changing climate patterns may impact IWW infrastructure resilience.

The findings are presented as tabulated index values across four-time intervals, starting from 1971 and extending to the end of the century. Additionally, graphical representations of the corresponding time series are included to provide a visual overview of trends and variations over time. A comprehensive dataset including the analysis for all five model setups and emission scenario will be available through the Mendeley platform as Digital Commons Data³. This comprehensive analysis helps to inform strategic planning and adaptive measures, ensuring that IWW infrastructures can effectively respond to future climatic challenges. Output of the operational modules of WP3 will support the operation of IWAT and other PLOTO components as implemented and demonstrated in WP6 and WP7. Furthermore, accumulated series of forecast variables (with data assimilation) is available for further analysis in the impact assessment modules of WP4.

³ The data is currently being uploaded and under review by the Mendeley Platform.

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